

Ordinal outcomes: a cumulative probability model with the identity link and constrained optimization

Gurbakhsh Singh¹, Gordon H. Fick²

¹Department of Mathematical Sciences, Central Connecticut State University, New Britain, Connecticut USA, 06053

²Department of Community Health Sciences, University of Calgary, Alberta, CANADA, T2N 4N1

Abstract

We present here a study of ordinal outcomes with a cumulative probability model but we consider the identity link and a 'proportional' assumption. The logit link is often used with ordinal outcomes in health research literature. With the logit link, one obtains the proportional odds model where regression coefficients are functions of cumulative odds. Recent work shows that when the log link and appropriate constraints are used, one obtains the proportional probability model where regression coefficients are functions of cumulative probabilities. However, when the identity link and appropriate parameters constraints are used, one obtains regression coefficients that are cumulative probabilities. We refer to this model as the additive probability model (APM). In using the identity link, cumulative risk differences can be estimated, and the number needed to treat.

For the APM, we present the model and its constraints. The Adaptive barrier method and Augmented Lagrangian are candidate constrained optimizers to determine the maximum likelihood estimates (MLEs). Simulations are conducted to compare optimizers across metrics: non-convergence rates, absolute log-likelihood difference, bias, root mean square error, and average optimization run time. Results of the simulation provide a suggested approach. We conclude with several examples and explorations including conditions for the uniqueness of the MLE and other features of the APM. This paper is primarily about introducing the APM and constrained optimization for determining its MLEs.

Key Words: generalized linear model, ordinal outcomes, identity link, additive probability model, constrained maximum likelihood estimation

1. Introduction

Recently, Blizzard et al.¹ and Singh & Fick² have provided exploration of generalized linear models for ordinal outcomes using a log link. They have chosen the log link instead of the logit link to provide models with interpretations of probabilities instead of odds. We will present the use of an identity link as another option with a probability interpretation in mind. However, the identity link introduces linear constraints upon the parameter spaces. For ordinal outcomes, the advantage of an identity link is the estimation of cumulative risk differences (cRD) and its reciprocal, the number needed to treat (NNT).

Through the identity link, the Non-Additive Model Probability Model (NPM) relates the cumulative probability of outcome variable y with J ordered categorical responses to the covariate vector x'_i ,

$$P(y \leq j | x_i) = \alpha_j + x'_i \beta_j$$

for cuts $j = 1, \dots, (J - 1)$ and subjects $i = 1, \dots, n$. There are parameters α_j and β_j for each cut j . The Additive Probability Model (APM) is a NPM which assumes the same $\beta_j = \beta$ for all cuts j . The APM assumes that $P(y \leq j)$ and $P(y \leq j')$ are additive. The constant of proportionality is $\alpha_j - \alpha_{j'}$ for $j \neq j'$. The linear inequality constraints in the APM are

- 1 from the identity link: $0 \leq \alpha_j + x_i' \beta \leq 1$ for $i = 1, \dots, n$ and $j = 1, \dots, (J - 1)$ which ensures $0 \leq P(y \leq j | x_i) \leq 1$ and
- 2 from the cumulative probability: $\alpha_j \leq \alpha_{j+1}$ which ensures a cumulative probability.

These constraints restrict the parameters space Ω_{APM} of the APM: $P(y \leq j | x_i) = \alpha_j + x_i' \beta$ to be

$$\Omega_{APM} = \{(\alpha, \beta) | 0 \leq \alpha_j + x_i' \beta \leq 1, \alpha_{j+1} \geq \alpha_j, j = 1, \dots, (J - 1), \forall i\},$$

where $\alpha = (\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_{J-1})'$, $\beta = (\beta_1, \dots, \beta_p)'$ and the boundaries are $\{(\alpha, \beta) | \alpha_j + x_i' \beta = 0\} \cup \{\alpha | \alpha_{j+1} = \alpha_j\} \cup \{(\alpha, \beta) | \alpha_j + x_i' \beta = 1\}$. We seek to optimize the likelihood function

$$L(\alpha, \beta) = c \prod_{i=1}^n \left[\prod_{j=1}^J \pi_j(x_i)^{y_{ij}} \right]$$

subject to these constraints. The estimation involves $(J - 1)$ components of α and p components of β . Let $y_i' = (y_{i1}, y_{i2}, \dots, y_{iJ})$ have components y_{ij} which denote the indicator for observation unit i and category j , where $i = 1, \dots, n$. The y_i' are assumed to be statistically independent and provide counts which are each multinomial distributions with probabilities $(\pi_1(x_i), \dots, \pi_J(x_i))$, where x_i' is i -th row of covariates of the $n \times p$ covariate matrix \mathbf{X} and $\sum_j \pi_j(x_i) = 1$. Using the cumulative probability $P(y \leq j | x_i) = \pi_1(x_i) + \dots + \pi_j(x_i)$ and $P(y = j | x_i) = \pi_j(x_i)$ we get $\{\pi_1(x_i) = P(y = 1 | x_i)$ and $\pi_j(x_i) = P(y \leq j | x_i) - P(y \leq j - 1 | x_i)$ for $j = 2, \dots, J - 1$ and $\pi_J(x_i) = 1 - P(y \leq J - 1 | x_i)\}$. Using this, the problem becomes optimize the log-likelihood function

$$\begin{aligned} \ell(\alpha, \beta) = & \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\sum_{j=2}^{J-1} y_{ij} \log[\alpha_j + x_i' \beta - (\alpha_{j-1} + x_i' \beta)] \right) + \sum_{i=1}^n y_{iJ} \log[1 - (\alpha_{J-1} + x_i' \beta)] \\ & + \sum_{i=1}^n y_{i1} \log[\alpha_1 + x_i' \beta] + G \end{aligned}$$

In a similar constrained optimization setting involving binary outcome and an identity link, Kovalchik *et al.*³ uses the adaptive barrier algorithm of Lange^{4,5} with the R function *constrOptim* to determine the MLE for an expit model. Schwendinger *et. al.*⁶ provided other optimization approaches, including the Augmented Lagrangian method using R function *auglag*. We applied both of these functions to compute the MLE for the APM.

We are compiling an R package called *apm* which contains preliminary function *apm* to determine the MLE for an APM with linear inequality constraints on the parameter space. This function permits the user to use either the R function *constrOptim* or the R function *auglag* both of which manage the linear inequality constraints of the APM.

In section 2.3 a brief simulation is conducted to assess the use of adaptive barrier algorithm and Augmented Lagrangian method to determine the MLE for the APM. In Sections 3.3 and A.2, the conditions for the uniqueness of the MLE are developed. Section 4 uses the function *apm* to determine the MLE for a couple dataset examples.

2. Constrained Optimization

Determining the MLE requires finding $(\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$ that maximizes $\ell(\alpha, \beta)$, subject to the constraints on the parameter space Ω_{APM} . This will be assessed using R function *constrOptim* and *auglag*.

2.1 Adaptive barrier method

constrOptim is a part of the *stats* package in R⁷. It provides an adaptive barrier optimization algorithm for the minimization of a function subject to equality and inequality constraints. To briefly introduce these details, we note that this minimization can be accomplished by constructing a surrogate function $\ell^*(\boldsymbol{\alpha}, \boldsymbol{\beta})$, which consists of a barrier function $b(\boldsymbol{\alpha}, \boldsymbol{\beta})$ and a positive tuning parameter μ . The surrogate function $\ell^*(\boldsymbol{\alpha}, \boldsymbol{\beta}) = -\ell(\boldsymbol{\alpha}, \boldsymbol{\beta}) + \mu b(\boldsymbol{\alpha}, \boldsymbol{\beta})$ is then minimized over decreasing values of μ (that is as $\mu \rightarrow 0, \ell^* \rightarrow -\ell$). The algorithm addresses the minimization problem of a convex function subject to the concave inequality constraints. The APM inequality constraints in *constrOptim* must be expressed as $-\alpha_j - x'_i \beta \geq 1, \alpha_j + x'_i \beta \geq 0$ and $\alpha_{j+1} - \alpha_j \geq 0$. This algorithm requires the specification of inequality constraints, the selection of feasible starting values, and the monitoring of circumstances when the MLE is on or near the boundary. The function permits different optimizers but we use the Nelder-Mead search method.

2.2 Augmented Lagrangian

auglag is a part of the *alabama*⁸ package in R. It provides an Augmented Lagrangian optimization algorithm for the minimization of a function subject to equality and inequality constraints which is useful for the APM. We note that this minimization can be accomplished by using a Lagrangian optimization approach that incorporates a penalty to handle the inequality constraints.

$$-\ell(\alpha, \beta) - \sum_i \lambda_i c_i(\alpha, \beta, \lambda, \sigma) + \frac{\sigma}{2} \sum_i c_i(\alpha, \beta, \lambda, \sigma)^2$$

With multiplier λ_i , modified constraints c_i and penalty parameter σ , but note that non-feasible starting values are permitted. The function permits the use of different optimizers but we use the default Broyden-Fletcher-Goldfarb-Shanno (BFGS) algorithm from the *optim* solver.

2.3 Simulation comparison

A simulation study is conducted using comparison metrics and simulation scenarios presented in binary outcome settings but now expanded to ordinal outcomes. The study compares constrained methods across different conditions. Each condition has N replicates with n observations each. There are three main simulation criterion described in sections 2.4-2.6. Optimizers are compared across 6 metrics:

- 1 Non-convergence (NCR): relative number of times the solver signaled non-convergence or other issue.
- 2 Absolute log-likelihood difference (ALLD): average absolute difference between the log-likelihood obtained by the solver and the highest log-likelihood obtained by all solvers $\ell(\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}^*)$:

$$ALLD = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N |\ell(\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_k) - \ell(\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}^*)|$$

- 3 Bias (BIAS) relative bias in percent determined by:

$$BIAS = \frac{100}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{\hat{\beta}_k - \beta_k}{\beta_k}$$

- 4 Root mean square error (RMSE): determined by:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N (\hat{\beta}_k - \beta_k)^2}$$

- 5 Simulation run time (RT).
- 6 % of N with MLE on boundary either MLE in $\Omega_0 = \{(\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta}) \mid \hat{\alpha}_j + x'_i \hat{\beta} \leq 0.00001\}$ or $\Omega_1 = \{(\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta}) \mid \hat{\alpha}_j + x'_i \hat{\beta} \geq 0.99999\}$

2.4 Simulation A

Simulation A: For 3 ordinal outcomes, 1000 replicates the following model was simulated,

$$P(y \leq j \mid x_1) = \alpha_j + x_1 \beta_1.$$

Across scenarios:

- 1 sample size $n \in \{100, 500\}$
- 2 $\alpha_1 = 0.25, \alpha_2 = 0.75, \beta_1 = 0.10$, and $x_1 \sim \text{Unif}[-2, 2]$
- 3 $\alpha_1 = 0.10, \alpha_2 = 0.75, \beta_1 = 0.10$, and $x_1 \sim \text{Unif}[-0.9, 0.9]$
- 4 $\alpha_1 = 0.10, \alpha_2 = 0.25, \beta_1 = 0.10$, and $x_1 \sim \text{Unif}[-0.9, 0.9]$

2.5 Simulation B

Simulation B: For 3 ordinal outcomes, 1000 replicates the following model was simulated,

$$P(y \leq j \mid E, x_2) = \alpha_j + E \beta_1 + x_2 \beta_2,$$

where E is the exposure status and β_1 is cumulative risk difference (cRD) common to $\{j = 1, 2\}$.
Across scenarios:

- 1 Different sample sizes: $n \in \{500, 5000, 50000\}$,
- 2 $\alpha_1 = 0.15, \alpha_2 = 0.25, \beta_1 = 0.30$, and $\beta_2 = 0.15$, and
- 3 $E \sim \text{Bin}[p = 0.5]$, and $x_2 \sim \text{Unif}[-1, 2]$.

2.6 Simulation C

Simulation C : focuses on generating simulation settings with many more covariates. The data is generated for 3 ordinal outcomes and $N = 1000$ replicates generated from:

$$P(y \leq j \mid x_k) = \alpha_j + \sum_{k=1}^p x_k \beta_k$$

Across scenarios:

- 1 $n = 500$
- 2 Number of Covariates: $p \in \{6, 10, 16, 50\}$
- 3 1: $\alpha_1 = 0.45, \alpha_2 = 0.55$, first half are $\beta_k = -0.01$, and remaining half are $\beta_k = 0.01$, and $x_k \sim \text{Bin}[p = 0.5]$

2.7 Simulation Results

The results of each simulation are presented in Tables 1 - 3 . The results from Simulation A show no significant difference in Bias, RMSE or ALLD. The assessment of MLE on a boundary is different in Scenario 1, which may depend on number significant digits. The Biases are fairly large for smaller sample sizes and decrease for larger sample sizes. The RMSE also decreases as sample size increases. We further note that Simulation B shows these same results. But we do note that as the sample size increases there is a small increase in the average run time. Simulation C, shows that as number of covariates increases, run time increases. This is when *constrOptim* and *auglag* performance times begin to diverge. It should be noted that the increase in covariates with a sample size of 500 may induce some separability which is anticipated to be a factor for MLE on a boundary.

Table 1: Results of Simulation A

Scenario	n	Method	Bias (%)	RMSE	ALLD	Ω_1	Ω_0
1	100	<i>constrOptim</i>	-2.29	0.024	3×10^{-7}	20.1%	0%
		<i>auglag</i>	-2.26	0.024	0.012	20.2%	0%
	500	<i>constrOptim</i>	-0.22	0.011	0.005	1.3%	0%
		<i>auglag</i>	-0.27	0.011	0.014	1.2%	0%
2	100	<i>constrOptim</i>	-6.52	0.043	5.6×10^{-6}	2%	0%
		<i>auglag</i>	-6.59	0.043	2.7×10^{-6}	2%	0%
	500	<i>constrOptim</i>	-1.61	0.011	0.013	0%	0%
		<i>auglag</i>	-1.76	0.019	0.007	0%	0%
3	100	<i>constrOptim</i>	-3.84	0.051	0.0003	0%	0%
		<i>auglag</i>	-3.91	0.051	6.3×10^{-6}	0%	0%
	500	<i>constrOptim</i>	-2.79	0.020	2.5×10^{-5}	0%	0%
		<i>auglag</i>	-2.89	0.020	3.5×10^{-5}	0%	0%

Table 2: Results of Simulation B

Sample size	Method	Avg. Time (s)	Bias (%)	RMSE	ALLD	Ω_1	Ω_0
500	<i>constrOptim</i>	< 1	-0.30	0.038	5.5×10^{-5}	0%	0%
	<i>auglag</i>	< 1	-0.25	0.038	5.3×10^{-5}	0%	0%
5000	<i>constrOptim</i>	~ 1	0.02	0.011	0.127	0%	0%
	<i>auglag</i>	1.076	0.05	0.011	0.041	0%	0%
50000	<i>constrOptim</i>	6.6	-0.12	0.004	0	0%	0%
	<i>auglag</i>	13.8	-0.08	0.003	0.004	0%	0%

Table 3: Results of Simulation C

p	Method	avg time (s)	non-convergence		Ω_1	Ω_0
			ALLD	(per 1000)		
6	<i>constrOptim</i>	~ 1	0	0	0%	0%
	<i>auglag</i>	~ 1	0.0002	0	0%	0%
10	<i>constrOptim</i>	24.08	0.0003	0	0%	0%
	<i>auglag</i>	~ 1	0.0004	0	0%	0%
16*	<i>constrOptim</i>	131	0.0147	0	0%	0%
	<i>auglag</i>	~ 1	0.0029	0	0%	0%
50*	<i>constrOptim</i>	1507	-	0	26%	0%
	<i>auglag</i>	14.1	-	0	26%	0%

3 Conditions for the uniqueness of the MLE

An MLE will be unique if there is only one maximum of the log-likelihood function. For generalized linear models, Wedderburn⁹ used strict concavity¹⁰ of the log-likelihood function to determine conditions for which there is at most one maximum of the log-likelihood function. This section contains the conditions for the uniqueness of the MLE for the APM.

Covariate matrix \mathbf{X} and response matrix \mathbf{Y} :

$$\mathbf{X} = \begin{bmatrix} x_{11} & x_{12} & \dots & x_{1p} \\ x_{21} & x_{22} & \dots & x_{2p} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ x_{n1} & x_{n2} & \dots & x_{np} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x'_1 \\ x'_2 \\ \vdots \\ x'_n \end{bmatrix} \text{ and corresponding outcomes } \begin{bmatrix} y'_1 \\ y'_2 \\ \vdots \\ y'_n \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} y_{11} & y_{12} & \dots & y_{1J} \\ y_{21} & y_{22} & \dots & y_{2J} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ y_{n1} & \dots & \dots & y_{nJ} \end{bmatrix}.$$

We now group by distinct covariate patterns. Let us define a second set of matrices \mathbf{C} and \mathbf{N} . \mathbf{C} contains the distinct covariate rows of \mathbf{X} . We suppose that \mathbf{C} is full column rank with $m \leq n$ different groups or covariate sets. For each row of \mathbf{C} , let n_{kj} denote the count of the number of outcomes for group k and category j . Let N denote a matrix of the (n_{kj}) counts of the number of outcomes for each group k and ordinal categories j . Also let $N^{(j)}$ be j -th column of N and let $N^{(-j)}$ be N without the j -th column. The matrices \mathbf{C} and \mathbf{N} are

$$\mathbf{C} = \begin{bmatrix} c_{11} & c_{12} & \dots & c_{1p} \\ c_{21} & c_{22} & \dots & c_{2p} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ c_{m1} & \dots & \dots & c_{mp} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} c'_1 \\ c'_2 \\ \vdots \\ c'_m \end{bmatrix} \text{ with counts } N = \begin{bmatrix} n_{11} & n_{12} & \dots & n_{1J} \\ n_{21} & n_{22} & \dots & n_{2J} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ n_{m1} & \dots & \dots & n_{mJ} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} n'_1 \\ n'_2 \\ \vdots \\ n'_m \end{bmatrix}.$$

Denote the sum of column j of N as $n^{(j)} = \sum_{k=1}^m n_{kj}$ and denote the sum of row k of N as $n_{(k)} = \sum_{j=1}^J n_{kj}$. Note that $n^{(j)} > 0$ and $n_{(k)} > 0$, otherwise the respective information for the column (category) or row (group) can be removed from the matrix N . We can also note that n'_k is Multinomial with the number of trials $n_{(k)}$ and probabilities $(\pi_1(c_k), \dots, \pi_J(c_k))$ where the n'_k are statistically independent.

The likelihood function can be expressed as: $l(\alpha, \beta) = \sum_{k=1}^m (\sum_{j=2}^{J-1} n_{kj} \log [\alpha_j - \alpha_{j-1}]) + \sum_{k=1}^m n_{kj} \log [1 - (\alpha_{j-1} + c'_k \beta)] + \sum_{k=1}^m n_{k1} \log [\alpha_1 + c'_k \beta] + G$.

Note that Ω_{APM} is a convex set. Denote the matrix which attaches the ones vector to the C matrix by $C^* = 1C$. Also let $I_k = \{k \mid n_{kj} = 0\}$ and $I_{k^*} = \{k \mid n_{k1} = 0\}$. Recall that N has column sum $n^{(j)} > 0$ and row sum $n_{(k)} > 0$

Theorem 1. For the APM and for $\{(\alpha, \beta) \mid \alpha_{j-1} + c'_k \beta < 1, 0 < \alpha_1 + c'_k \beta, \alpha_{j+1} > \alpha_j\}$:

- 1 If C^* is full column rank and if both $n_{k1} \neq 0, n_{kj} \neq 0$ for all k then the H is negative definite and the log-likelihood is strictly concave.
- 2 If both $m - |I_k| \geq (p + 1)$ and $m - |I_{k^*}| \geq (p + 1)$ and both $C_{-I_k}^*$ and $C_{-I_{k^*}}^*$ are full column rank then the H is negative definite and the log-likelihood is strictly concave.
- 3 If either $m - |I_k| < (p + 1)$ or $m - |I_{k^*}| < (p + 1)$ then the H is negative semi-definite and the log-likelihood is concave.

The details and the proof of Theorem 1 is presented in Appendix A.2. Theorem 1 shows that the log-likelihood for the APM is concave with restrictions for strict concavity based on counts in N and if $C_{-I_k}^*$ and $C_{-I_{k^*}}^*$ are full column rank. These conditions can be assessed using functions in R.

4. Examples

We present two examples: Example 4.1 and 4.2 which determine the MLE and the impact of reverse coding. Both examples are computed using *constrOptim*. Appendix A.1 presents the Hessian and approach to compute the estimates of the standard errors (SE).

4.1 Example 1: Tonsil Dataset

In this example, we consider the Tonsil dataset in McCullagh¹¹, which is given in Table 4. There are 1,398 observations pertaining to the outcome of the size of tonsils: 1 - not enlarged, 2 enlarged, and 3 - greatly enlarged. The covariate here is an indicator variable for carrier ($x = \{0,1\}$) for non-carriers and carriers of *Streptococcus pyogenes*. Using this data, the following model is assumed: $P(y \leq j \mid x) = \alpha_j + \beta_1 x$, where $C \mid N$ is

$$C \mid N = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 497 & 560 & 269 \\ 1 & 19 & 29 & 24 \end{bmatrix},$$

and where $J = 3$ and $j = 1,2$. Note that $C^* = 1C$ is full column rank and the log-likelihood is strictly concave from Theorem 1.

Carrier Status	Not Enlarged	Enlarged	Greatly Enlarged	Total
non-carrier	497	560	269	1326
carrier	19	29	24	72
Total	516	589	293	1398

The MLE and estimated standard error from *apm* are presented on the left in Table 5. For the model $P(y \leq j \mid x) = \alpha_j + \beta_1 x$, the interpretation of β_1 is common to both cuts ($j = 1,2$) with $\beta_1 = P(y \leq j \mid x = 1) - P(y \leq j \mid x = 0)$. $\hat{\beta}_1$ estimates the difference of cumulative probabilities for

carriers relative to non-carriers. This is an estimate of the cumulative risk difference of $\hat{\beta}_1 = -0.1198$ (95% $CI(-0.2080, -0.0315)$) is a reduction in the cumulative probability (assumed common to both cuts $j = 1, 2$) of having a tonsil size less than or equal to cut j for carriers than non-carriers. Where $j = 1$ corresponds to not enlarged and $j = 2$ corresponds to enlarged or not enlarged. This would provide an estimate of the $NNT = 8.347$ and a 95% confidence interval estimate of NNT of (4.807, 31.736).

We also note that if the outcome was reversely coded: 3 - not enlarged, 2 - enlarged and 1 - greatly enlarged, the model could be rewritten as $1 - P(y \leq j | x) = \kappa_j + \gamma_1 x$ and $\gamma_1 = (1 - P(y \leq j | x = 0)) - (1 - P(y \leq j | x = 1))$. This would imply that $\gamma_1 = -\beta_1$. The MLE from *apm* are compared in the right portion of Table 5. For the logit and probit links, the relationship between the MLE for the forward and reversely coded outcome is a sign change. However, for the identity link, the estimates of the intercept/cut is 1-Probability and the sign changes for the covariates between the MLE for the forward and reversely coded outcome, that is: $\hat{\kappa}_1 = 1 - \hat{\alpha}_2$, $\hat{\kappa}_2 = 1 - \hat{\alpha}_1$, and $\hat{\gamma}_1 = -\hat{\beta}_1$. The estimated standard errors are as expected given the relationships between α and κ as well as β and γ .

Table 5: MLE by CFE and *apm* for Example 4.1

MLE	<i>apm</i>	SE	MLE	<i>apm</i>	SE
$\hat{\alpha}_1$	0.3755	0.0132	$\hat{\kappa}_1$	0.2032	0.0110
$\hat{\alpha}_2$	0.7968	0.0110	$\hat{\kappa}_2$	0.6245	0.0132
$\hat{\beta}_1$	-0.1198	0.0450	$\hat{\gamma}_1$	0.1198	0.0450

4.2 Example 2: Endometrial Cancer Dataset

We now consider data collected from a study of endometrial cancer by Hill et al.¹². The study involves 288 women diagnosed with endometrial cancer. Explanatory variables include: Race (x_1 : coded as 0 - white and 1 - black) and Estrogen (x_2 : coded as 0 - not used and 1 - used). Ordinal outcomes are tumor grade (coded 2 - well differentiated, 1 - moderately differentiated, and 0 - poorly differentiated). Using this data, we will explore the following model: $P[y \leq j | x_1, x_2] = \alpha_j + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2$.

$$C | N = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 15 & 31 & 24 \\ 0 & 1 & 16 & 41 & 79 \\ 1 & 0 & 18 & 28 & 19 \\ 1 & 1 & 4 & 5 & 6 \end{bmatrix}$$

Table 6: MLE for Example 4.2

MLE	<i>apm</i>	SE	MLE	<i>apm</i>	SE
$\hat{\alpha}_1$	0.2299	0.0450	$\hat{\kappa}_1$	0.4030	0.0474
$\hat{\alpha}_2$	0.5970	0.0474	$\hat{\kappa}_2$	0.7701	0.0450
$\hat{\beta}_1$	0.0934	0.0562	$\hat{\gamma}_1$	-0.0934	0.0561
$\hat{\beta}_2$	-0.1199	0.0482	$\hat{\gamma}_2$	0.1199	0.0482

For the model $P(y \leq j | x_1, x_2) = \alpha_j + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2$, the interpretation of β_2 is assumed common to both cuts and assumed common to blacks and whites with $\beta_2 = P(y \leq j | x_2 = 1) - P(y \leq j | x_2 = 0)$. $\hat{\beta}_2$ estimates the difference of cumulative probabilities for those receiving Estrogen and those not receiving Estrogen assumed common to race and cuts. The difference from the APM is estimated as -0.1199.

We also note that if the outcome was reversely coded: 0 - well differentiated, 1 - moderately differentiated, and 2 - poorly differentiated. The model could be rewritten as $1 - P(y \leq j | x_1, x_2) = \kappa_j + \gamma_1 x_1 + \gamma_2 x_2$. The MLE is presented in the right portion of Table 6. As indicated in Example 4.1, for the identity link, the estimates of the intercept/cut is 1- Probability and the sign changes for the covariates between the MLE for the forward and reversely coded outcome, that is: $\hat{\kappa}_1 = 1 - \hat{\alpha}_2, \hat{\kappa}_2 = 1 - \hat{\alpha}_1, \hat{\gamma}_1 = -\hat{\beta}_1$, and $\hat{\gamma}_2 = -\hat{\beta}_2$. The estimated standard errors are as expected given the relationships between α and α as well as β and γ .

5. Discussion

This manuscript expands the understanding and methodology of the APM for use by a data analyst. The condition for the strict concavity of the log-likelihood requires assessment of the rank of C_{-j}^* .

There has been significant discussion in the literature on misinterpretations of odds as probabilities. The APM gives estimates of the probability. These estimates are typically of interest to analysts in the health sciences. The trade off for the APM providing such estimates is that the identity link implicitly introduces linear inequality constraints on the parameter space. We feel that since the function *apm* uses a constrained optimization methodology of *constrOptim* and *auglag*, the MLE can be determined reliably in the interior and on the boundary of the parameter space. This was shown through several simulations. The main advantage of *auglag* over *constrOptim* appears to be run time when there are many covariates. Bias, RMSE, ALLD, and percent on a boundary all appear comparable between the two optimizers.

We note that additional investigation is required for the exact conditions for an MLE on a boundary. However, having groups for which $n_{kj} = 0$ appears to play a role for an MLE on boundary Ω_1 and $n_{k1} = 0$ appears to play a role for an MLE on boundary Ω_0 . The use of measured explanatory variables may introduce some groups with $n_{k1} = 0$ and/or $n_{kj} = 0$. Another consideration is the use of the covariance matrix from the inverse of the negative observed Hessian when an MLE is on a boundary. The analyst should assess the behavior of the Hessian near a boundary. In any case, the interpretation of such a covariance matrix may be limited and its utility might be misleading.

For ordinal outcomes, the choice to use the identity link is now available, and this choice can be based on the study design, the measure of association and the interpretation(s) desired. We have shown the utility of the function *apm* and are compiling a preliminary version of the R package *apm*.

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Appendix

A.1 Score Hessian functions

The score function $S(\alpha, \beta) = (S'_\alpha, S'_\beta)'$ is a $(J - 1 + p) \times 1$ vector consisting of $(J - 1) \times 1$ vector S'_α of derivatives of the log-likelihood with respect to α_j for $j = 1, \dots, (J - 1)$ and $p \times 1$ vector S'_β of derivatives of the log-likelihood with respect to β_l for $l = 1, \dots, p$. The elements of S_β are given by:

$$\frac{\partial l(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \beta_l} = - \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{n_{kJ} c_{kl}}{1 - (\alpha_{J-1} + c'_k \beta)} + \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{n_{k1} c_{kl}}{\alpha_1 + c'_k \beta},$$

which is defined for $\{(\alpha_{j-1}, \beta) 0 < \alpha_{j-1} + c'_k \beta < 1\}$ and $\{(\alpha_1, \beta) p < \alpha_1 + c'_k \beta < 1\}$ and the elements of S_α are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial l(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \alpha_1} &= - \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{n_{k2}}{\alpha_2 - \alpha_1} + \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{n_{k1}}{\alpha_1 + c'_k \beta}, \\ \frac{\partial l(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \alpha_{j-1}} &= - \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{n_{kJ}}{1 - (\alpha_{j-1} + c'_k \beta)} + \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{n_{k(j-1)}}{\alpha_{j-1} - \alpha_{j-2}}, \\ \frac{\partial l(\alpha, \beta | X)}{\partial \alpha_j} &= - \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{n_{k(j+1)}}{\alpha_{j+1} - \alpha_j} + \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{n_{kj}}{\alpha_j - \alpha_{j-1}}. \end{aligned}$$

and for $1 < j < J - 1$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial l(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \alpha_1} &= - \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{n_{k2}}{\alpha_2 - \alpha_1} + \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{n_{k1}}{\alpha_1 + c'_k \beta}, \\ \frac{\partial l(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \alpha_{j-1}} &= - \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{n_{kJ}}{1 - (\alpha_{j-1} + c'_k \beta)} + \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{n_{k(j-1)}}{\alpha_{j-1} - \alpha_{j-2}}, \\ \frac{\partial l(\alpha, \beta | X)}{\partial \alpha_j} &= - \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{n_{k(j+1)}}{\alpha_{j+1} - \alpha_j} + \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{n_{kj}}{\alpha_j - \alpha_{j-1}}. \end{aligned}$$

The observed Fisher Information matrix $-\mathbf{H}$ is used in the estimation of the variance of the parameters¹³. The Hessian is a patterned matrix,

$$\mathbf{H} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{H}_{\alpha\alpha} & \mathbf{H}_{\alpha\beta} \\ \mathbf{H}'_{\alpha\beta} & \mathbf{H}_{\beta\beta} \end{bmatrix}.$$

$\mathbf{H}_{\alpha\alpha}$ is a $(J - 1) \times (J - 1)$ tri-band matrix of the associated second derivatives with respect to α and is denoted:

$$\mathbf{H}_{\alpha\alpha} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & A_{23} & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & A_{23} & A_{33} & A_{34} & \dots & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & A_{34} & A_{44} & \dots & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & A_{J-3,J-3} & A_{J-2,J-3} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & A_{J-2,J-3} & A_{J-2,J-2} & A_{J-2,J-1} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & A_{J-2,J-1} & A_{J-1,J-1} \end{bmatrix}.$$

$\mathbf{H}_{\alpha\beta}$ is a $(J-1) \times p$ matrix of zeros with two rows consisting of the mixed derivatives with respect to α and β and is denoted:

$$\mathbf{H}_{\alpha\beta} = \begin{bmatrix} M_{11} & M_{12} & M_{13} & \dots & M_{1(p-1)} & M_{1p} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ M_{(J-1)1} & M_{(J-1)2} & M_{(J-1)3} & \dots & M_{(J-1)(p-1)} & M_{(J-1)p} \end{bmatrix}.$$

$\mathbf{H}_{\beta\beta}$ is a $p \times p$ matrix of the second derivatives with respect to β and is denoted:

$$\mathbf{H}_{\beta\beta} = \begin{bmatrix} B_{11} & B_{12} & \dots & B_{1(p-1)} & B_{1p} \\ B_{21} & B_{22} & \dots & B_{2(p-1)} & B_{2p} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ B_{(p-1)1} & B_{(p-1)2} & \dots & B_{(p-1)(p-1)} & B_{(p-1)p} \\ B_{p1} & B_{p2} & \dots & B_{p(p-1)} & B_{pp} \end{bmatrix}.$$

In assessing the terms, denote $\delta_{kj} = \frac{n_{kj}}{(1-(\alpha_{j-1}+c'_k\beta))^2}$, $\delta_{k1} = \frac{n_{kj}}{(\alpha_1+c'_k\beta)^2}$ and also $\gamma_{k,j+1} = \frac{n_{k,j+1}}{(\alpha_{j+1}-\alpha_j)^2}$.

The second derivatives are:

$$\begin{aligned} B_{a1} &= \frac{\partial^2 l(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \beta_o \partial \beta_1} = - \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{n_{kj} c_{kl} c_{ko}}{(1-(\alpha_{j-1} + c'_k \beta))^2} - \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{n_{k1} c_{kd} c_{ko}}{(\alpha_1 + c'_k \beta)^2} \\ &= - \sum_{k=1}^m c_{kl} c_{ko} \delta_{kj} - \sum_{k=1}^m c_{kl} c_{ko} \delta_{k1}, \\ M_{11} &= \frac{\partial^2 l(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \alpha_1 \partial \beta_1} = - \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{n_{k1} c_{kl}}{(\alpha_1 + c'_k \beta)^2} \\ &= - \sum_{k=1}^m c_{kl} \delta_{k1}, \\ M_{(J-1)1} &= \frac{\partial^2 l(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \alpha_{j-1} \partial \beta_1} = - \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{n_{kj} c_{kl}}{(1-(\alpha_{j-1} + c'_k \beta))^2} \\ &= - \sum_{k=1}^m c_{kl} \delta_{kj}, \end{aligned}$$

for $1 < j < (J-1)$, $M_{j1} = 0$. Notation for the derivatives of the log-likelihood with respect to the α will be denoted by A_{st} where s,t are the associated α_s and α_t . The second derivatives are:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^2 l(\boldsymbol{\alpha}, \boldsymbol{\beta})}{\partial \alpha_1^2} &= -\sum_{k=1}^m \frac{n_{k2}}{(\alpha_2 - \alpha_1)^2} - \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{n_{k1}}{(\alpha_1 + c'_k \beta)^2} \\
&= -\sum_{k=1}^m \gamma_{k2} - \sum_{k=1}^m \delta_{k1}, \\
\frac{\partial^2 l(\boldsymbol{\alpha}, \boldsymbol{\beta})}{\partial \alpha_{j-1}^2} &= -\sum_{k=1}^m \frac{n_{kJ}}{\left(1 - (\alpha_{j-1} + c'_k \beta)\right)^2} - \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{n_{k(j-1)}}{(\alpha_{j-1} - \alpha_{j-2})^2} \\
&= -\sum_{k=1}^m \delta_{kJ} - \sum_{k=1}^m \gamma_{k(j-1)}, \\
\frac{\partial^2 l(\boldsymbol{\alpha}, \boldsymbol{\beta})}{\partial \alpha_{j-1}^2} &= -\sum_{k=1}^m \frac{n_{kJ}}{\left(1 - (\alpha_{j-1} + c'_k \beta)\right)^2} - \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{n_{k(j-1)}}{(\alpha_{j-1} - \alpha_{j-2})^2} \\
&= -\sum_{k=1}^m \delta_{kJ} - \sum_{k=1}^m \gamma_{k(j-1)}
\end{aligned}$$

and for $1 < j < (J - 1)$:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^2 l(\boldsymbol{\alpha}, \boldsymbol{\beta})}{\partial \alpha_j^2} &= -\sum_{k=1}^m \frac{n_{k(j+1)}}{(\alpha_{j+1} - \alpha_j)^2} - \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{n_{kj}}{(\alpha_j - \alpha_{j-1})^2} \\
&= -\sum_{k=1}^m \gamma_{k(j+1)} - \sum_{k=1}^m \gamma_{kj}, \\
\frac{\partial^2 l(\boldsymbol{\alpha}, \boldsymbol{\beta})}{\partial \alpha_1 \partial \alpha_2} &= -\sum_{k=1}^m \frac{n_{k2}}{(\alpha_2 - \alpha_1)^2} \\
&= -\sum_{k=1}^m \gamma_{k2}, \\
\frac{\partial^2 l(\boldsymbol{\alpha}, \boldsymbol{\beta})}{\partial \alpha_{j-2} \partial \alpha_{j-1}} &= -\sum_{k=1}^m \frac{n_{k(j-1)}}{(\alpha_{j-1} - \alpha_{j-2})^2} \\
&= -\sum_{k=1}^m \gamma_{k(j-1)}, \\
\frac{\partial^2 l(\boldsymbol{\alpha}, \boldsymbol{\beta})}{\partial \alpha_{j-1} \partial \alpha_j} &= -\sum_{k=1}^m \frac{n_{kj}}{(\alpha_j - \alpha_{j-1})^2} \\
&= -\sum_{k=1}^m \gamma_{kj}, \\
\frac{\partial^2 l(\boldsymbol{\alpha}, \boldsymbol{\beta})}{\partial \alpha_{j+1} \partial \alpha_j} &= -\sum_{k=1}^m \frac{n_{k(j+1)}}{(\alpha_{j+1} - \alpha_j)^2} \\
&= \gamma_{k(j+1)}
\end{aligned}$$

A2. Proof of conditions for uniqueness of MLE

The proof of the conditions for strict concavity for the log-likelihood function for the APM is as follows: Proof of Theorem 1.

Begin by noting that Ω_{APM} is a convex set. This is easily established noting for the APM, the parameter space is $\Omega_{APM} = \{(\alpha, \beta) \mid 0 \leq \alpha_j + x_i' \beta \leq 1, \alpha_{j+1} \geq \alpha_j\}$. Suppose $\epsilon_1 \in \Omega_{APM}, \epsilon_2 \in \Omega_{APM}$ and constant $\gamma \in [0,1]$. Let $\epsilon^* = \gamma \epsilon_1 + (1 - \gamma) \epsilon_2$ and

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{X}\epsilon^* &= \mathbf{X}(\gamma \epsilon_1 + (1 - \gamma) \epsilon_2) \\ &= \gamma \underbrace{\mathbf{X}\epsilon_1}_{\in [0,1]} + (1 - \gamma) \underbrace{\mathbf{X}\epsilon_2}_{\in [0,1]} \\ &\in [0,1] \end{aligned}$$

$\epsilon^* \in \Omega_{APM}$ and Ω_{APM} is a convex set.

To establish the concavity of the interior of the parameter space, it can be shown that $\mathbf{z}'\mathbf{H}\mathbf{z} < 0$ for all $\mathbf{z} \neq \mathbf{0}$. By the block matrix form of the Hessian, define $\mathbf{z}' = (\xi', \zeta') = (\underbrace{\xi_1, \xi_2, \dots, \xi_{J-1}}_{\xi}, \underbrace{\zeta_1, \zeta_2, \dots, \zeta_p}_{\zeta'})$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{z}'\mathbf{H}\mathbf{z} &= [\xi' \zeta'] \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{H}_{\alpha\alpha} & \mathbf{H}_{\alpha\beta} \\ \mathbf{H}'_{\alpha\beta} & \mathbf{H}_{\beta\beta} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \xi \\ \zeta \end{bmatrix} \\ &= \underbrace{\xi' \mathbf{H}_{\alpha\alpha} \xi}_{(1)} + \underbrace{\xi' \mathbf{H}_{\alpha\beta} \zeta}_{(2)} + \underbrace{\zeta' \mathbf{H}'_{\alpha\beta} \xi}_{(3)} + \underbrace{\zeta' \mathbf{H}_{\beta\beta} \zeta}_{(4)}. \end{aligned}$$

The following is the result of simplifying the above quadratic form:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{z}'\mathbf{H}\mathbf{z} &= - \sum_{k=1}^m \left[\sum_{r=1}^{J-2} \frac{n_{k(r+1)}}{(\alpha_{r+1} - \alpha_r)^2} (\xi_r + \xi_{r+1})^2 \right] \\ &\quad - \sum_{k=1}^m \left[\frac{n_{kJ}}{(1 - (\alpha_{J-1} + c'_k \beta))^2} \left(\xi_{J-1} + \sum_{l=1}^p c_{kl} \zeta_l \right)^2 \right] \\ &\quad - \sum_{k=1}^m \left[\frac{n_{k1}}{(\alpha_1 + c'_k \beta)^2} \left(\xi_1 + \sum_{l=1}^p c_{kl} \zeta_l \right)^2 \right]. \end{aligned}$$

From this $\mathbf{z}'\mathbf{H}\mathbf{z} \leq 0$, \mathbf{H} is negative semidefinite and the log-likelihood is concave. However, additional conditions can be provided for which the log-likelihood is strictly concave. Recall that N has $n^{(s)} > 0$ and $n^{(k)} > 0$. Let $\{(\alpha_1, \alpha_{J-1}, \beta) \mid \alpha_{j-1} + c'_k \beta < 1, 0 < \alpha_1 + c'_k \beta, \alpha_{j+1} > \alpha_j\}$. Also let $\mathbf{z}'\mathbf{H}\mathbf{z} = T_1 + T_2 + T_3$, where:

$$\begin{aligned}
T_1 &= - \sum_{k=1}^m \left[\sum_{r=1}^{J-2} \underbrace{n_{k(r+1)}}_{\geq 0} \underbrace{\frac{1}{(\alpha_{r+1} - \alpha_r)^2}}_{> 0} \underbrace{(\xi_r + \xi_{r+1})^2}_{\geq 0} \right], \\
T_2 &= - \sum_{k=1}^m \left[\underbrace{[n_{kj}]_{\geq 0}}_{> 0} \underbrace{\frac{1}{(1 - (\alpha_{j-1} + c'_k \beta))^2}}_{> 0} \underbrace{\left(\xi_{j-1} + \sum_{l=1}^p c_{kl} \zeta_l \right)^2}_{\geq 0} \right], \\
T_3 &= - \sum_{k=1}^m \left[\underbrace{[n_{k1}]_{\geq 0}}_{> 0} \underbrace{\frac{1}{(\alpha_1 + c'_k \beta)^2}}_{> 0} \underbrace{\left(\xi_1 + \sum_{l=1}^p c_{kl} \zeta_l \right)^2}_{\geq 0} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

1. Suppose \mathbf{C}^* and both $n_{k1} \neq 0, n_{kj} \neq 0$ for all k . For $\mathbf{z}'\mathbf{H}\mathbf{z} = T_1 + T_2 + T_3$ to sum to 0, $T_1 = 0, T_2 = 0$ and $T_3 = 0$.

$$T_2 = - \sum_{k=1}^m \left[\underbrace{[n_{kj}]_{> 0}}_{> 0} \underbrace{\frac{1}{(1 - (\alpha_{j-1} + c'_k \beta))^2}}_{> 0} \underbrace{\left(\xi_{j-1} + \sum_{l=1}^p c_{kl} \zeta_l \right)^2}_{\geq 0} \right]$$

For $T_2 = 0, \xi_{j-1} + \sum_{l=1}^p c_{kl} \zeta_l = 0$ for $k = 1, \dots, m$. This represents rows of the system $\mathbf{C}^* \boldsymbol{\epsilon}'_{j-1} = \mathbf{0}$, where $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}'_{j-1} = (\xi_{j-1}, \boldsymbol{\zeta}')$. Since \mathbf{C}^* is full column rank, it has linear independent columns and so $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{j-1} = \mathbf{0}$.

$$T_3 = - \sum_{k=1}^m \left[\underbrace{[n_{k1}]_{> 0}}_{> 0} \underbrace{\frac{1}{(\alpha_1 + c'_k \beta)^2}}_{> 0} \underbrace{\left(\xi_1 + \sum_{l=1}^p c_{kl} \zeta_l \right)^2}_{\geq 0} \right]$$

For $T_3 = 0, \xi_1 + \sum_{l=1}^p c_{kl} \zeta_l = 0$ for $k = 1, \dots, m$. This represents rows of the system $\mathbf{C}^* \boldsymbol{\epsilon}'_1 = \mathbf{0}$, where $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}'_1 = (\xi_1, \boldsymbol{\zeta}')$. Since \mathbf{C}^* is full column rank, it has linear independent columns and so $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_1 = \mathbf{0}$.

$$T_1 = - \sum_{k=1}^m \left[\sum_{r=1}^{J-2} \underbrace{n_{k(r+1)}}_{\geq 0} \underbrace{\frac{1}{(\alpha_{r+1} - \alpha_r)^2}}_{> 0} \underbrace{(\xi_r + \xi_{r+1})^2}_{\geq 0} \right]$$

For $T_1 = 0, n_{k(r+1)} = 0$ or $(\xi_r + \xi_{r+1}) = 0$ or both. From the construction of N , the row total ($n_{(k)} > 0$) and column totals ($n^{(j)} > 0$) are non-zero. Thus, for each $j = 1, \dots, J-2$, there is a k for which $n_{k(j+1)} > 0$. For these $k, \xi_r + \xi_{r+1} = 0$ for $r = 1, \dots, J-2$ and $\xi_r = -\xi_{r+1}$.

From $T_3 = 0, T_2 = 0$ it is determined that $\xi_{j-1} = 0$ and $\xi_1 = 0$ and working recursively, $\xi_r = 0$ for $r = 1, \dots, J-1$. Finally, $\xi = 0$ and $T_1 = 0$.

$\xi' H_{\alpha\alpha} \xi + \xi' H_{\alpha\beta} \zeta + \zeta' H'_{\alpha\beta} \xi + \zeta' H_{\beta\beta} \zeta < 0$ with equality when $\xi = \mathbf{0}$ and $\zeta = \mathbf{0}$. \mathbf{H} is negative definite and the log-likelihood function is strictly concave¹⁰.

2. Suppose $m - |I_k| \geq (p+1)$ and $m - |I_{k^*}| \geq (p+1)$ and suppose both $\mathbf{C}^*_{-I_k}$ and $\mathbf{C}^*_{-I_{k^*}}$ are full column rank. For $\mathbf{z}'\mathbf{H}\mathbf{z} = T_1 + T_2 + T_3$ to sum to 0, $T_1 = 0, T_2 = 0$ and $T_3 = 0$.

$$T_2 = - \sum_{k \notin I_k} [\underbrace{n_{kj}}_{>0} \frac{1}{\underbrace{(1 - (\alpha_{j-1} + c'_k \beta))}_{>0}} \underbrace{\left(\xi_{j-1} + \sum_{l=1}^p c_{kl} \zeta_l \right)}_{\geq 0}]^2$$

For $T_2 = 0$ for $k \notin I_k$, $\xi_{j-1} + \sum_{l=1}^p c_{kl} \zeta_l = 0$. This represents rows of the system $C_{-I_k}^* \epsilon_{j-1} = 0$, where $\epsilon'_{j-1} = (\xi_{j-1}, \zeta')$. Since $C_{-I_k}^*$ is full column rank, it has linear independent columns and so $\epsilon_{j-1} = \mathbf{0}^-$.

$$T_3 = - \sum_{k \notin I_k} [\underbrace{n_{k1}}_{>0} \frac{1}{\underbrace{(\alpha_1 + c'_k \beta)^2}_{>0}} \underbrace{\left(\xi_1 + \sum_{l=1}^p c_{kl} \zeta_l \right)}_{\geq 0}]^2$$

For $T_3 = 0$ for $k \notin I_{k^*}$, $\xi_1 + \sum_{l=1}^p c_{kl} \zeta_l = 0$. This represents rows of the system $C_{-I_{k^*}}^* \epsilon_1 = 0$, where $\epsilon'_1 = (\xi_1, \zeta')$. Since $C_{-I_{k^*}}^*$ is full column rank, it has linear independent columns and so $\epsilon_1 = \mathbf{0}$.

$$T_1 = - \sum_{k=1}^m \left[\sum_{r=1}^{J-2} \underbrace{n_{k(r+1)}}_{\geq 0} \frac{1}{\underbrace{(\alpha_{r+1} - \alpha_r)^2}_{>0}} \underbrace{(\xi_r + \xi_{r+1})^2}_{\geq 0} \right]$$

For $T_1 = 0$, $n_{k(r+1)} = 0$ or $(\xi_r + \xi_{r+1}) = 0$ or both. From the construction of N , the row total ($n_{(k)} > 0$) and column totals ($n^{(j)} > 0$) are non-zero. Thus, for each $j = 1, \dots, J-2$, there is a k for which $n_{k(j+1)} > 0$. For these k , $\xi_r + \xi_{r+1} = 0$ for $r = 1, \dots, J-2$ and $\xi_r = -\xi_{r+1}$. From $T_3 = 0, T_2 = 0$ it is determined that $\xi_{j-1} = 0$ and $\xi_1 = 0$ and working recursively, $\xi_r = 0$ for $r = 1, \dots, J-1$. Finally, $\xi = 0$ and $T_1 = 0$. Combining this information, $\mathbf{z}' \mathbf{H} \mathbf{z} < 0$ with equality when $\xi = \mathbf{0}$ and $\zeta = \mathbf{0}$. \mathbf{H} is negative definite and the log-likelihood function is strictly concave ¹⁰.

3. Suppose either $m - |I_k| < (p+1)$ or $m - |I_{k^*}| < (p+1)$. For $\mathbf{z}' \mathbf{H} \mathbf{z} = T_1 + T_2 + T_3$ to sum to 0, $T_1 = 0, T_2 = 0$ and $T_3 = 0$.

$$T_2 = - \sum_{k \in I_k} [\underbrace{n_{kj}}_{>0} \frac{1}{\underbrace{(1 - (\alpha_{j-1} + c'_k \beta))}_{>0}} \underbrace{\left(\xi_{j-1} + \sum_{l=1}^p c_{kl} \zeta_l \right)}_{\geq 0}]^2$$

For $T_2 = 0$ for $k \in I_k$, $\xi_{j-1} + \sum_{l=1}^p c_{kl} \zeta_l = 0$. However, if $m - |I_k| < (p+1)$ and the number of rows of the system $C_{-I_k}^* \epsilon_{j-1} = \mathbf{0}$ are fewer than the number of columns. There is a non-trivial solution to this system and $\epsilon_{j-1} \neq \mathbf{0}$.

$$T_3 = - \sum_{k \in I_{k^*}} [\underbrace{n_{k1}}_{>0} \frac{1}{\underbrace{(\alpha_1 + c'_k \beta)^2}_{>0}} \underbrace{\left(\xi_1 + \sum_{l=1}^p c_{kl} \zeta_l \right)}_{\geq 0}]^2$$

For $T_3 = 0$ for $k \in I_{k^*}$, $\xi_1 + \sum_{l=1}^p c_{kl} \zeta_l = 0$. However, if $m - |I_{k^*}| < (p+1)$ the number of rows of the system $C_{-I_{k^*}}^* \epsilon_1 = \mathbf{0}$ are fewer than the number of columns, where $\epsilon'_1 = (\xi_1, \zeta')$. There is a non-trivial solution to this system and $\epsilon_1 \neq \mathbf{0}$.

Whichever holds: $m - |I_k| < (p + 1)$ or $m - |I_{k^*}| < (p + 1)$ (or both), then there is a non-trivial solution to their respective systems. Combining this information, $\mathbf{z}'\mathbf{H}\mathbf{z} \leq 0$ with for all \mathbf{z} . \mathbf{H} is negative semi-definite and the log-likelihood function is concave¹⁰. Additional consideration is required for this item dependent on the different combinations of the conditions. This is left as future research.

A.3 Appendix Score Test of Proportionality

In ordinal regression models the proportionality assumption is testable. For example the likelihood ratio test¹⁴, the Wald (or Brant) test¹⁵, or the score test¹⁶. The APM from Section 2 assumes that different levels of the ordinal outcomes share a common slope β . This can be tested using the hypothesis: $H_0: \beta_1 = \beta_2 = \dots = \beta_{j-1}$ for the general model NPM.

For $j = 1, \dots, J - 1$. Let the parameter vector for NPM be $\Phi = (\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_{j-1}, \beta'_1, \beta'_2, \dots, \beta'_{j-1})'$. Denote the score statistic S_R :

$$S_R = S'_{NPM}(\hat{\Phi}_0)(-\mathbf{H}_{NPM})^{-1}S_{NPM}(\hat{\Phi}_0),$$

where S_{NPM} is the score function and $-\mathbf{H}_{NPM}$ is the negative Hessian function for the NPM, $\hat{\Phi}_0$ is the MLE from APM. The test statistic S_R is χ^2 distributed with $df = (J - 2)p$.

Recall the example in Section 4.1, which was about patient tonsil size and status as carriers of Streptococcus pyogene. The MLEs for an APM are found in Table 5. The assessment of proportionality gives test statistic $S_R = 0.1082$, $df = 1$ and p - value = 0.7422. Here, there is no evidence against the additive assumption.

Recall the example in Section 4.2, which included a dataset for women with endometrial cancer. The MLEs for a APM are found in Table 6. The assessment of proportionality gives test statistic $S_R = 5.1286$, $df = 2$ and p - value = 0.077. Here, there is not sufficient evidence against the additive assumption.

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